

EXPERIENTIAL PERSPECTIVE ON THE APPLICATION OF TACROLIMUS IN ATOPIC DERMATITIS TREATMENT

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Abstract: *Data on the mechanisms of formation and methods of effective treatment of atopic dermatitis (AD) are presented. The main directions of pathogenetically based treatment of blood pressure, differentiated correction of concomitant pathology are described in detail. The external therapy of atopic skin lesions in children with the use of modern dermatological cosmetics is presented in particular detail.*

Keywords: *Atopic dermatitis, treatment, tacrolimus.*

Introduction: Atopic dermatitis (atopic eczema, atopic eczema/dermatitis syndrome) is a chronic inflammatory skin disease accompanied by itching, which in typical cases begins in early childhood, can continue or recur in adulthood and leads to physical and emotional maladaptation of the patient and his family members. Atopic dermatitis in childhood and adulthood is a single disease, despite the fact that in the future, genetic subtypes with different expression variants may be isolated. Atopic dermatitis in most cases develops: It occurs in people with a hereditary predisposition and is often combined with other allergic diseases, such as bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis, food allergies, as well as with recurrent skin infections. ICD10: L20 Atopic dermatitis. Abbreviations: RAST - radioallergosorbent test; MGK - local glucocorticoids; UV - ultraviolet: voe (irradiation). The prevalence of the disease has increased over the past 3 decades and is in developed countries, according to various authors, 10:15% in children under the age of 5 years and 15: 20% in schoolchildren. The reasons for the increase in morbidity are unknown. On the other hand, in some agricultural regions of China, Eastern Europe and Africa, the incidence rate remains at the same level. It was found that atopic dermatitis develops in 81% of children if both parents are sick, in 59% - if only one of the parents is sick, and the other has an allergic pathology of the respiratory tract, and in 56% - if only one of the parents is sick.

Aim: Determination of the effectiveness of 0.05% tacrolimus ointment (Tacropic drug) in the external therapy of atopic dermatitis.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted on the basis of the regional dermatovenereological dispensary. The study included 26 patients with atopic dermatitis aged 6 to 14 years, skin lesions in the examined patients averaged 14%. Other skin diseases and infectious pathology were excluded. Together with standard treatment, 11 patients with atopic dermatitis of the study group received 0.05% tacrolimus ointment externally twice a day, rubbing a thin layer into the skin, the remaining 10 patients made up the control group and received topical glucocorticosteroids of medium strength and benogam cream, the course of external therapy was 28 days. These groups were comparable in terms of the main clinical

indicators, gender, age, and concomitant pathology. The effectiveness of therapy was monitored based on the dynamics of values (before the start of the study, on the 14th and 28th days of therapy), sleep assessment and subjective symptoms (itching, dryness and soreness of the skin).

Results and discussion. All patients tolerated external therapy with 0.03% tacrolimus ointment (Tacropic drug) well, no undesirable effects were detected. Already on the 14th day of therapy, hyperemia, swelling, infiltration decreased in 10 patients of the study group, the intensity of itching subjectively decreased, sleep was restored, which was not observed in patients of the comparison group, by the 28th day of treatment therapy, 100% clinical recovery was observed in patients of the main group compared with the control group, in which 80% clinical recovery was observed for the treatment period of 28 days. In the control group, complete clinical recovery was observed on day 35 of the treatment.

Conclusions. As a result of our research, we came to the conclusion that the 0.05% tacrolimus ointment (Tacropic drug) used by us demonstrates high safety and efficacy in the treatment of atopic dermatitis, allowing us to stop subjective and objective signs of the disease in a short time.

LITERATURE:

1. Iskandarovna K. M. SIFILISNING IMMUNOASSAY SHAKLLARI //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 534-536.
2. Iskandarovna K. M., Dilshodovna A. D., Adxamovna A. A. Impact of Socio-Hygienic Conditions of Life on the Health of Students //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 644-646.
3. Iskandarovna K. M. et al. Comprehensive Assessment of the Levels of Somatic Health and Disturbances of Adaptation Reserves in Medical Students //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 641-643.

4. Iskandarovna K. M., Alamovich K. A., Rabbimovich N. A. Treatment of Urethrogonic Prostatitis Associated with Chlamydia Infection //TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 44-46.
5. Iskandarovna K. M., Buribaevna I. S., Azamovna A. N. Immunoassay Forms of Syphilis //TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 47-49.
6. Ахмедова М. М., Абдуллаев Х. Д., Камолова М. И. ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ МЕТОДОВ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ОНИХОМИКОЗОВ У ВЗРОСЛЫХ //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKSHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 186-190.
7. Абдуллаев Д. М., Абдуллаев Х. Д., Камолова М. И. ОПЫТ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ КРЕМАТЕРБИЗИЛ ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ МИКОЗОВ //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKSHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 181-185.
8. Davlatovich A. X. VAGINAL TRIXOMONADLAR SH TAMMASINI TRIXOPOLGA VA XIMOTRIPSIN BILAN BILAN SEZGICHLIGINI ANIQLASH //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKSHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 645-647.
9. Davlatovich A. X., Orifovich S. D., Baxtiyorovich A. S. Studying the Relationship of Local Immune Status and the Course of Burn Disease //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 679-682.
10. Xolmurodovich D. J., Umidovich N. T., Davlatovich A. X. CLINIC COURSE OF NONSPECIFIC PNEUMONIA //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKSHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 510-513.
11. Абдуллаев Х. Д. и др. ЛАЗЕР В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ВИТИЛИГО //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKSHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 495-500.
12. Hikmatovich I. N. et al. The use of Fungite in the Local Treatment of

Genital Herpes //International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 5. – C. 231-232.

13. Davlatovich A. X., O'gli A. B. X., O'gli I. A. S. BOLALARDA GENITAL GERPESNI DAVOLASH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 367-369.

14. Xolmurodovich D. J., Orifovich R. S., Davlatovich A. X. FEATURES OF THE MICROELEMENT STATUS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ATOPIC DERMATITIS IN CHILDREN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 447-450.

15. Davlatovich A. X. DETERMINATION OF GENE ACTIVITY IN VITILIGO PATIENTS //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 451-454.

16. Tolibov M. M., qizi Buronova F. Z. MAHALLIY OZON TERAPIYASINI QO 'LLAGAN HOLDA KOMPLEKS DAVOLASH FONIDA YOSH ERKAKLARDA SURUNKALI URETROGEN PROSTATIT (CUP) KECHISHINI O 'RGANISH //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 417-421.

17. Tolibov M. M., Shodmonova M. A. BOLALARDA ATOPIK DERMATIT (AD) PATOGENEZIDA GENETIK OMILLARNING ROLINI BAHOLASH VA IMMUNOLOGIK PARAMETRLARGA QARAB ANIQLANGAN POLIMORFIZMLARNING PROGNOZIK AHAMIYATINI ANIQLASH //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 406-410.

18. Tolibov M. M. et al. ATOPIK DERMATITNI DAVOLASHDA LAZER TERAPIYASINING SAMARADORLIGI //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 286-289.

19. Utayev A. J., Tolibov M. M., Axmedova M. M. MANAGEMENT APPROACHES FOR CHRONIC URETHROGENIC PROSTATITIS //Modern

Scientific Research International Scientific Journal. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 151-156.

20. Makhmudovich T. M. ATOPIC DERMATITIS INCIDENT LEVEL, DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA AND PROGNOSTIC IMPORTANCE //JOURNAL OF APPLIED MEDICAL SCIENCES. – 2023. – Т. 6. – №. 4. – С. 158-168.

21. Толибов М. М. СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМ ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИИ, МИКРОБИОЛОГИИ И ТЕРАПИИ АКНЕ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ) //SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 215-224.

22. Иляевна Р. У. et al. DERMATOSCOPIC PAINTING SOME COMMON DERMATOSES //World scientific research journal. – 2023. – Т. 16. – №. 2. – С. 107-120.

23. Иляевна Р. У. et al. MODERN TRENDS IN TREATMENT SICK MICROSPORIA //World scientific research journal. – 2023. – Т. 16. – №. 2. – С. 98-106.

24. Kholikovich E. S. et al. APPLICATION OF" BETASALIK" OINTMENT IN THE THERAPY OF CHRONIC INFLAMMATORY AND ALLERGIC DERMATOSES //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – Т. 31. – №. 3. – С. 56-62.

25. Мансур Т. М., Вохидов Ж. Ж. СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛЕЗНИ ВИТИЛИГО //SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 234-244.

26. Мансур Т. М., Вохидов Ж. Ж. СОВРЕМЕННОЙ МЕТОДЫ АЛОПЕЦИЯ ДИАГНОСТИКА И ЛЕЧЕНИЕ //SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 225-233.

27. Толибов М. М. и др. ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ К ЛЕЧЕНИЮ ТЯЖЕЛЫХ ОБОЖЖЕННЫХ БОЛЬНЫХ //SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 190-199.

28. Абдуллаев Д. М., Тошев С. У., Толибов М. М. КОМПЛЕКСНЫЙ МЕТОД ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ВУЛЬГАРНЫХ УГРЕЙ //Актуальные аспекты медицинской деятельности. – 2021. – С. 254-256.

29. Абдуллаев Х., Толибов М. Allergodermatozlar bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan vulgar asneni kompleks davolash Samaraligini o‘rganish //Журнал гепатогастроэнтерологических исследований. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3.2. – С. 73-74.